

EXPLORING THE TOURISM POTENTIAL OF DUMAGUETE CITY: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

This research study entitled “Exploring the Tourism Potential of Dumaguete City: Opportunities and Challenges” aimed to explore the tourism potential of the city. Among 207 validated self-made survey questionnaire was used to gather data from tourism staff, tourist (foreign and domestic), and business owner or managers. Statistical tools such as Mean, Composite Mean, and Pearson Correlation Coefficient were applied to analyzed the data. Results of the study shows that respondents were generally satisfied with the current tourism potential of Dumaguete City. Additionally, findings revealed that Dumaguete City has strong tourism potential, particularly in terms of tourism site, which received high positive perceptions from all respondents. Infrastructure and facilities, were identified as challenges to tourism in Dumaguete City, with respondents perceived to moderately agreeing (composite mean 3.05, 3.68, and 3.62). Tourism services and promotion and marketing strategies were also evaluated positively, contributing to overall tourist satisfaction. The study concludes that Dumaguete City has great potential to become a leading tourist destination in Negros Oriental, provided that the identified challenges are properly addressed. The study established a significant relationship between the current tourism profile and the level of satisfaction of respondents, implying that improvements in tourism components directly influence visitor experiences.

Keywords: *Opportunities and Challenges, Tourism Sites, Infrastructure and Facilities, Tourism services, Promotion and Marketing strategies, 22 Tourism Staff, 150 Tourists (Foreign and Domestic), 35 Business Owners/Managers of Hotel.*

INTRODUCTION

Tourism is a major driver of the global economy, contributing to employment, cultural exchange, and sustainable development (Le, 2024). Over time, the demand for travel increased due to higher incomes, more leisure time, and changing lifestyles, with people traveling for recreation, culture, and pilgrimage. Before the pandemic, international tourism reached 1.465 billion arrivals in 2019. However, the COVID-19 pandemic caused a sharp decline, reducing arrivals to 917 million in 2022 (World Travel & Tourism Council [WTTC], 2022). The industry experienced severe losses in 2020 and 2021, and although tourism began to recover in 2022, it remained below pre-pandemic levels. These challenges highlighted the vulnerability of the tourism sector to global crises, as well as the need for resilience and sustainable strategies.

In the Philippines, tourism plays an important role in economic growth and cultural promotion. The country had strong potential due to its rich cultural heritage, diverse natural resources, and growing eco-tourism and community-based tourism initiatives. Government programs, such as “Love the Philippines,” aimed to attract both local and international visitors (Department of Tourism [DOT], 2023). In Dumaguete City, the Negros Oriental Tourism Board worked to identify new tourist destinations and promote the region’s attractions (Partlow, 2023). These efforts supported local businesses and highlighted the cultural and natural assets of the area, helping position the Philippines as a competitive destination in the global tourism market.

Despite these developments, there was limited research focusing specifically on Dumaguete City’s tourism potential. Most studies in the Philippines examined tourism in broader contexts or in other locations, such as farm tourism and heritage tourism, rather than focusing on smaller or emerging cities (Veranga, 2024; Felicilda & Reyes, 2025). Existing literature also tended to highlight general tourism trends, opportunities, and challenges at the national level without providing detailed analysis of specific local destinations (Abari & Malibiran, 2024). In addition, studies on Central Philippines mainly focused on spatial distribution of accommodations and major tourism hubs, offering limited discussion on the overall tourism experience and competitiveness of cities like Dumaguete (Lopez, 2025). Furthermore, research on Dumaguete itself remained limited and often concentrated only on specific aspects, such as service quality in selected sectors, leaving other important areas underexplored (Toledo, 2025).

Therefore, this study aimed to assess the tourism potential of Dumaguete City by examining its key attractions, including Rizal Boulevard, St. Catherine of Alexandria Cathedral, and the National Museum of the Philippines Dumaguete, as well as its restaurants, facilities, and services. It also evaluated visitor satisfaction in terms of accessibility, amenities, hospitality, and overall experience. Furthermore, the study identified the opportunities and challenges affecting tourism development and provided recommendations to help local stakeholders and policymakers improve the city’s tourism industry and support sustainable growth.

Research Questions

This study sought to assess the tourism profile of Dumaguete City by measuring visitor satisfaction and identifying the opportunities and challenges faced by local sectors. It also aimed to determine whether tourists' perceptions of the city's tourism profile significantly corresponded with their level of satisfaction.

1. What is the current tourism profile of Dumaguete City in terms of:
 - 1.1 tourism site;
 - 1.2 infrastructure and facilities; and
 - 1.3 tourism services.
2. What is the respondents' level of satisfaction of Tourism Potentials of Dumaguete City in terms of:
 - 2.1 tourism site;
 - 2.2 infrastructure and facilities; and
 - 2.3 tourism services?
3. What is the extent of the respondents' perception of the opportunities created by tourism in Dumaguete City?
4. What is the extent of the respondents' perception of the challenges affecting tourism development in Dumaguete City?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the current tourism profile and the respondents' level of satisfaction of the Dumaguete tourism potentials?

METHODOLOGY

Research design. This study utilized a descriptive correlational research design, which involved collecting data from different individuals at a single point in time. In correlational research, the relationships between variables were identified and examined without manipulating any of them.

In addition, this study employed a quantitative approach, using a questionnaire as the main data-gathering tool. It focused on obtaining objective measurements and applying statistical analysis to describe and explain the tourism potentials in Dumaguete City. The main goal was to gather numerical data that could be analyzed, compared across groups, and used to draw meaningful insights about the opportunities and challenges of tourism in Dumaguete City.

Research respondents. The respondents of this study included tourism staff, domestic and foreign tourists, and business owners or managers who were directly involved in or affected by tourism activities. These groups were selected because they had relevant experiences and insights related to the tourism potential of the area.

A purposive sampling technique was used to identify the respondents. This method ensured that only individuals with adequate knowledge and experience in tourism were

included in the study, allowing for more meaningful and relevant responses regarding tourism experiences and benefits.

The selection of respondents aimed to gather in-depth insights into their perceptions and experiences in Dumaguete City. A total of 207 respondents were included in the study. Below is the distribution of the respondents:

Group of Respondents	No.of Respondents
Tourism Staff	22
Tourists (foreign and locals)	150
Business Owners/ Managers	35
Total	207

Research Instruments. In this study, the researchers utilized a validated self-made survey questionnaire. The questionnaire was carefully structured to gather relevant information on the tourism potential, opportunities, and challenges in Dumaguete City.

The first part of the questionnaire presented the purpose of the study and provided clear instructions to guide respondents in answering the survey accurately and easily. It also included the respondents' profile such as age and gender.

To ensure the validity of the instrument, the questionnaire was reviewed by three master teachers and an expert in the field of research. They examined the content for clarity, relevance, and consistency of the indicators. All comments, corrections, and suggestions provided by the validators were carefully considered and incorporated to improve the final version of the instrument.

A pilot test or dry run was conducted to determine the reliability of the questionnaire. Ten respondents participated in the pilot testing. Cronbach's alpha was used to measure internal consistency. The results showed that all indicators obtained reliability scores above 0.70, confirming that the instrument was reliable. Therefore, the survey questionnaire was considered both valid and reliable for use in the study.

The results of the pilot testing are presented below:

Questionnaire's indicators	Cronbach Alpha
Extent of Tourism profile	0.81
Level of Satisfactions	0.83
Extent of Perception on the Opportunities	0.80

Questionnaire's indicators	Cronbach Alpha
Extent of Perception on the Challenges	0.79

RESULTS

Table 1.1.1 presents the tourism staff's perception of the tourism sites in Dumaguete City, focusing on various attractions and their contribution to the city's overall tourism appeal. The results show a composite mean of 4.75, interpreted as "very high," which indicates that respondents have had a very positive assessment of the city as a tourism destination.

Table 1.1.2 presents the perception of tourists regarding the tourism sites in Dumaguete City. It has described how visitors have evaluated key attractions in terms of appeal, atmosphere, clarity of information, cultural value, and culinary contribution to the city's tourism image. The composite mean of 4.43, interpreted as "very high."

Table 1.1.3 presents the assessment of business owners regarding the tourism sites in Dumaguete City. It shows how local entrepreneurs perceive the city's major attractions and their contribution to the overall tourism profile. The composite mean of 4.22, interpreted as "very high,"

Table 1.2.1 Indicators stating that the city has adequate safety and security measures for tourists assessed by tourism staff got a highest mean score of 4.59, interpreted as very high. The lowest mean score among the indicators under infrastructure and facilities for tourism staff is the Communication networks (internet, mobile signal) are reliable in all tourist areas got a mean score of 4.00, interpreted as high. The composite mean score of this table is 4.27, interpreted as very high.

Table 1.1.1
Current Tourism Profile of Dumaguete City in terms of Tourism Site as Perceived by Tourism Staff

Tourism Site	\bar{w}_x	Verbal Description
1. Dumaguete City has a wide variety of tourist attractions that appeal to different interests.	4.45	Strongly Agree
2. Rizal Boulevard provides a relaxing and enjoyable atmosphere for both tourists and locals visiting Dumaguete City.	4.95	Strongly Agree
3. The information provided in the National museum of Dumaguete City is clear for both local and foreign tourists.	4.77	Strongly Agree
4. The Bell Tower of St. Catherine of Alexandria Cathedral is a culturally and historically significant attraction that enhances the overall tourism appeal of Dumaguete City.	4.82	Strongly Agree
5. Sans Rival Bistro & Bakery significantly adds to the city's tourism profile by offering high-quality food that tourists regularly seek out.	4.73	Strongly Agree

Composite	4.75	Strongly Agree
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree
	Verbal Equivalent	
	Very High	
	High	
	Moderately High	
	Low	
	Very Low	

Table 1.1.2
Current Tourism Profile of Dumaguete City in terms of Tourism Site as Perceived by Tourist

Tourism Site	\bar{w}_x	Verbal Description
1. Dumaguete City has a wide variety of tourist attractions that appeal to different interests.	4.37	Strongly Agree
2. Rizal Boulevard provides a relaxing and enjoyable atmosphere for both tourists and locals visiting Dumaguete City.	4.53	Strongly Agree
3. The information provided in the National museum of Dumaguete City is clear for both local and foreign tourists.	4.35	Strongly Agree
4. The Bell Tower of St. Catherine of Alexandria Cathedral is a culturally and historically significant attraction that enhances the overall tourism appeal of Dumaguete City.	4.51	Strongly Agree
5. Sans Rival Bistro & Bakery significantly adds to the city's tourism profile by offering high-quality food that tourists regularly seek out.	4.40	Strongly Agree
Composite	4.43	Strongly Agree

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 1.1.3
Current Tourism Profile of Dumaguete City in terms of Tourism Site as Perceived by Business Owner

Tourism Site	\bar{w}_x	Verbal Description
1. Dumaguete City has a wide variety of tourist attractions that appeal to different interests.	4.00	Agree
2. Rizal Boulevard provides a relaxing and enjoyable atmosphere for both tourists and locals visiting Dumaguete City.	4.34	Strongly Agree
3. The information provided in the National museum of Dumaguete City is clear for both local and foreign tourists.	4.11	Agree

4. The Bell Tower of St. Catherine of Alexandria Cathedral is a culturally and historically significant attraction that enhances the overall tourism appeal of Dumaguete City.	4.31	Strongly Agree
5. Sans Rival Bistro & Bakery significantly adds to the city's tourism profile by offering high-quality food that tourists regularly seek out.	4.34	Strongly Agree
Composite	4.22	Strongly Agree

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 1.2.1
Current Tourism Profile of Dumaguete City in terms of Infrastructure and Facilities as Perceived by Tourism Staff

Infrastructure and Facilities	\bar{w}_x	Verbal Description
1. Roads and transportation systems make traveling to tourist spots convenient.	4.27	Strongly Agree
2. Public facilities (e.g., restrooms, waiting areas) are clean and functional.	4.14	Agree
3. Accommodation facilities (hotels, inns, resorts) are comfortable and affordable.	4.36	Strongly Agree
4. The city has adequate safety and security measures for tourists.	4.59	Strongly Agree
5. Communication networks (internet, mobile signal) are reliable in all tourist areas.	4.00	Agree
Composite	4.27	Strongly Agree

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 1.2.2 The indicator accommodation facilities (hotels, inns, resorts) are comfortable and affordable gain the highest mean score of 4.14, interpreted as high. The lowest mean of the indicator public facilities is clean and functional got a mean score of 3.81, interpreted as high. The table shows that the composite mean score is 3.98, which is interpreted as high.

Table 1.2.2
Current Tourism Profile of Dumaguete City in terms of Infrastructure and Facilities as Perceived by Tourist

Infrastructure and Facilities	\bar{w}_x	Verbal Description
1. Roads and transportation systems make traveling to tourist spots convenient.	3.91	Agree
2. Public facilities (e.g., restrooms, waiting areas) are clean and functional.	3.81	Agree
3. Accommodation facilities (hotels, inns, resorts) are comfortable and affordable.	4.14	Agree
4. The city has adequate safety and security measures for tourists.	4.11	Agree
5. Communication networks (internet, mobile signal) are reliable in all tourist areas.	3.93	Agree
Composite	3.98	Agree

Legend:	<table border="0"> <tr> <td style="text-align: right;">Scale</td> <td style="text-align: left;">Verbal Description</td> <td style="text-align: left;">Verbal Equivalent</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4.21 – 5.00</td> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>Very High</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3.41 – 4.20</td> <td>Agree</td> <td>High</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2.61 – 3.40</td> <td>Moderately Agree</td> <td>Moderately High</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1.81 – 2.60</td> <td>Disagree</td> <td>Low</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1.00 – 1.80</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>Very Low</td> </tr> </table>	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low
Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent																	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High																	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High																	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High																	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low																	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low																	

Table 1.2.3 The data present that the highest mean score of 4.17 is the indicator accommodation facilities are comfortable and affordable, which interpreted as high. The business owners indicates that the accommodation establishments in Dumaguete City provides affordability and comfort for tourist. Furthermore, the indicator public facilities are clean and functional had a lowest mean score of 3.20, interpreted as Moderately high by the business owner.

Table 1.3.1 Perceived by the tourism staff with the indicator of tour guides are knowledgeable and accommodating obtained the highest mean of 4.77, interpreted as Strongly Agree. The two indicators some restaurants in Dumaguete City provide quality local and international food and tour packages and activities meet tourist’s expectations both got the lowest mean of 4.55, interpreted as Strongly Agree. The composite result of this table is 4.65, interpreted as very high.

Table 1.3.2 The indicator stating tourism office provides excellent customer service obtained the highest mean of 4.17, interpreted as high, indicating that tourist have a positive insight of the customer service given by the tourism office in Dumaguete City.

Table 1.2.3
Current Tourism Profile of Dumaguete City in terms of Infrastructure and Facilities as Perceived by Business Owner

Infrastructure and Facilities	\bar{w}_x	Verbal Description
1. Roads and transportation systems make traveling to tourist spots convenient.	3.74	Agree
2. Public facilities (e.g., restrooms, waiting areas) are clean and functional.	3.20	Moderately Agree
3. Accommodation facilities (hotels, inns, resorts) are comfortable and affordable.	4.17	Agree
4. The city has adequate safety and security measures for tourists.	3.83	Agree
5. Communication networks (internet, mobile signal) are reliable in all tourist areas.	3.60	Agree
Composite	3.71	Agree

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 1.3.1
Current Tourism Profile of Dumaguete City in terms of Tourism Services as Perceived by Tourism Staff

Tourism Services	\bar{w}_x	Verbal Description
1. Tour guides are knowledgeable and accommodating.	4.77	Strongly Agree
2. Tourism office provides excellent customer service.	4.73	Strongly Agree
3. Transportation services are safe, efficient, and tourist friendly.	4.64	Strongly Agree
4. Some Restaurants in Dumaguete City provide quality local and international food.	4.55	Strongly Agree
5. Tour packages and activities meet tourists' expectations.	4.55	Strongly Agree
Composite	4.65	Strongly Agree

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 1.3.2
Current Tourism Profile of Dumaguete City in terms of Tourism Services as Perceived by Tourist

Tourism Services	\bar{w}_x	Verbal Description
1. Tour guides are knowledgeable and accommodating.	4.16	Agree
2. Tourism office provides excellent customer service.	4.17	Agree
3. Transportation services are safe, efficient, and tourist friendly.	4.08	Agree
4. Some Restaurants in Dumaguete City provide quality local and international food.	4.31	Strongly Agree
5. Tour packages and activities meet tourists' expectations.	4.20	Agree
Composite	4.18	Agree

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 2.1.1 shows that the indicator experience and enjoyment in visiting tourist attractions obtained the highest mean score of 4.59, interpreted as “Very Satisfied.” In contrast, the indicator availability of informative signages and guides at tourist sites obtained the lowest mean score of 4.41, although it is still interpreted as “Very Satisfied.” The composite mean of is 4.49, interpreted as “Very Satisfied.”

Table 2.1.1
Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Tourism Potentials of Dumaguete City in terms of Tourism Site as Perceived by Tourism Staff

Tourism Site	\bar{w}_x	Verbal Description
1. Variety of tourist attractions in Dumaguete.	4.45	Very Satisfied
2. Cleanliness and maintenance of attractions in Rizal Boulevard.	4.50	Very Satisfied
3. Friendliness and helpfulness of local people and staff.	4.50	Very Satisfied
4. Availability of informative signages and guides at tourist sites.	4.41	Very Satisfied
5. Experience and enjoyment in visiting tourist attractions.	4.59	Very Satisfied
Composite	4.49	Very Satisfied

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Very Satisfied
3.41 – 4.20	Satisfied
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Dissatisfied
1.00 – 1.80	Very Dissatisfied

Table 2.1.2 shows that the indicator experience and enjoyment in visiting tourist attractions obtained the highest mean score of 4.39, interpreted as “Very Satisfied.” In contrast, the lowest mean score of 4.03 was recorded for the cleanliness and maintenance of attractions in Rizal Boulevard. The composite mean of 4.20, interpreted as “Satisfied.”

Table 2.1.2
Respondents’ Level of Satisfaction of Tourism Potentials of Dumaguete City in terms of Tourism Site as Perceived by Tourist

Tourism Site	\bar{w}_x	Verbal Description
1. Variety of tourist attractions in Dumaguete.	4.27	Very Satisfied
2. Cleanliness and maintenance of attractions in Rizal Boulevard.	4.03	Satisfied
3. Friendliness and helpfulness of local people and staff.	4.20	Satisfied
4. Availability of informative signages and guides at tourist sites.	4.13	Satisfied
5. Experience and enjoyment in visiting tourist attractions.	4.39	Very Satisfied
Composite	4.20	Satisfied

Legend: Scale Verbal Description
 4.21 – 5.00 Very Satisfied
 3.41 – 4.20 Satisfied
 2.61 – 3.40 Moderate
 1.81 – 2.60 Dissatisfied
 1.00 – 1.80 Very Dissatisfied

Table 2.2.1 shows that the availability of accommodation that meets tourists’ needs obtained the highest mean score of 4.32, interpreted as “Very Satisfied.” In contrast, the accessibility of roads and transportation to tourist sites received the lowest mean score of 4.18, interpreted as “Satisfied.”

Table 2.2.1
Respondents’ Level of Satisfaction of Tourism Potentials of Dumaguete City in terms of Infrastructure and Facilities as Perceived by Tourism Staff

Infrastructure and Facilities	\bar{w}_x	Verbal Description
1. Accessibility of roads and transportation to tourist spots.	4.18	Satisfied
2. Availability of public facilities (restrooms, signage, parking).	4.27	Very Satisfied
3. Safety and convenience of infrastructure provided.	4.27	Very Satisfied
4. The availability of accommodation that meets tourist needs.	4.32	Very Satisfied
5. Walkways, sidewalks, and pedestrian safety.	4.27	Very Satisfied
Composite	4.26	Very Satisfied

Legend: Scale Verbal Description
 4.21 – 5.00 Very Satisfied

3.41 – 4.20 Satisfied
 2.61 – 3.40 Moderate
 1.81 – 2.60 Dissatisfied
 1.00 – 1.80 Very Dissatisfied

Table 2.2.2 shows that the availability of accommodation that meets tourists 'needs obtained the highest mean score of 4.11, interpreted as "Satisfied." On the other hand, the availability of public facilities received the lowest mean score of 3.95, also interpreted as "Satisfied."

Table 2.2.2
Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Tourism Potentials of Dumaguete City in terms of Infrastructure and Facilities as Perceived by Tourist

Infrastructure and Facilities	\bar{wx}	Verbal Description
1. Accessibility of roads and transportation to tourist spots.	3.96	Satisfied
2. Availability of public facilities (restrooms, signage, parking).	3.95	Satisfied
3. Safety and convenience of infrastructure provided.	4.05	Satisfied
4. The availability of accommodation that meets tourist needs.	4.11	Satisfied
5. Walkways, sidewalks, and pedestrian safety.	4.09	Satisfied
Composite	4.03	Satisfied

Legend: Scale Verbal Description
 4.21 – 5.00 Very Satisfied
 3.41 – 4.20 Satisfied
 2.61 – 3.40 Moderate
 1.81 – 2.60 Dissatisfied
 1.00 – 1.80 Very Dissatisfied

Table 2.2.3 shows that the availability of accommodation that meets tourists 'needs obtained the highest mean score of 4.03, interpreted as "Satisfied." Meanwhile, the availability of public facilities recorded the lowest mean score of 3.37, interpreted as "Moderately Satisfied."

Table 2.2.3
Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Tourism Potentials of Dumaguete City in terms of Infrastructure and Facilities as Perceived by Business Owner

Infrastructure and Facilities	\bar{wx}	Verbal Description
1. Accessibility of roads and transportation to tourist spots.	3.60	Satisfied
2. Availability of public facilities (restrooms, signage, parking).	3.37	Moderate
3. Safety and convenience of infrastructure provided.	3.66	Satisfied
4. The availability of accommodation that meets tourist needs.	4.03	Satisfied
5. Walkways, sidewalks, and pedestrian safety.	3.69	Satisfied
Composite	3.67	Satisfied

Legend: Scale Verbal Description

4.21 – 5.00 Very Satisfied
 3.41 – 4.20 Satisfied
 2.61 – 3.40 Moderate
 1.81 – 2.60 Dissatisfied
 1.00 – 1.80 Very Dissatisfied

Table 2.3.1 shows that the indicator hospitality and friendliness of locals obtained the highest mean score of 4.82, interpreted as “Very Satisfied.” On the other hand, the indicator availability and quality of local tour guides received the lowest mean score of 4.50, although it is still interpreted as “Very Satisfied.”

Table 2.3.1
Respondents’ Level of Satisfaction of Tourism Potentials of Dumaguete City in terms of Tourism Services as Perceived by Tourism Staff

Tourism Services	\bar{w}_x	Verbal Description
1. Hospitality and friendliness of locals.	4.82	Very Satisfied
2. Hotel and lodging services.	4.59	Very Satisfied
3. Food services and restaurant in Dumaguete.	4.73	Very Satisfied
4. Availability and quality of local tour guide.	4.50	Very Satisfied
5. The responsiveness of tourism offices to inquiries.	4.68	Very Satisfied
Composite	4.66	Very Satisfied

Legend: Scale Verbal Description
 4.21 – 5.00 Very Satisfied
 3.41 – 4.20 Satisfied
 2.61 – 3.40 Moderate
 1.81 – 2.60 Dissatisfied
 1.00 – 1.80 Very Dissatisfied

Table 2.3.2 shows that the indicator food services and restaurants in Dumaguete obtained the highest mean score of 4.41, interpreted as “Very Satisfied.” In comparison, the indicators availability and quality of local tour guides and responsiveness of tourism offices to inquiries both received the lowest mean score of 4.21, interpreted as “Very Satisfied.”

Table 2.3.2
Respondents’ Level of Satisfaction of Tourism Potentials of Dumaguete City in terms of Tourism Services as Perceived by Tourist

Tourism Services	\bar{w}_x	Verbal Description
1. Hospitality and friendliness of locals.	4.31	Very Satisfied
2. Hotel and lodging services.	4.30	Very Satisfied
3. Food services and restaurant in Dumaguete.	4.41	Very Satisfied
4. Availability and quality of local tour guide.	4.21	Very Satisfied
5. The responsiveness of tourism offices to inquiries.	4.21	Very Satisfied

Composite **4.29** **Very Satisfied**

Legend: **Scale** **Verbal Description**
 4.21 – 5.00 Very Satisfied
 3.41 – 4.20 Satisfied
 2.61 – 3.40 Moderate
 1.81 – 2.60 Dissatisfied
 1.00 – 1.80 Very Dissatisfied

Table 2.3.3 shows that the indicator food services and restaurants in Dumaguete obtained the highest mean score of 4.54, interpreted as “Very Satisfied.” The indicator responsiveness of tourism offices to inquiries recorded the lowest mean score of 3.80, interpreted as “Satisfied.”

Table 2.3.3
Respondents’ Level of Satisfaction of Tourism Potentials of Dumaguete City in terms of Tourism Services as Perceived by Business Owner

Tourism Services	<i>wx</i>	Verbal Description
1. Hospitality and friendliness of locals.	4.37	Very Satisfied
2. Hotel and lodging services.	4.23	Very Satisfied
3. Food services and restaurant in Dumaguete.	4.54	Very Satisfied
4. Availability and quality of local tour guide.	3.91	Satisfied
5. The responsiveness of tourism offices to inquiries.	3.80	Satisfied
Composite	4.17	Satisfied

Legend: **Scale** **Verbal Description**
 4.21 – 5.00 Very Satisfied
 3.41 – 4.20 Satisfied
 2.61 – 3.40 Moderate
 1.81 – 2.60 Dissatisfied
 1.00 – 1.80 Very Dissatisfied

Table 3.1.1 presents the extent of respondents’ perception of the economic opportunities generated by tourism in Dumaguete City as perceived by tourism staff. The findings show a composite mean of 4.25, interpreted as “Strongly Agree” and “Very High,”

Table 3.1.1
Extent of the Respondents’ Perception of the Opportunities created by Tourism in Dumaguete City in terms of Economic Opportunities as Perceived by Tourism Staff

Economic Opportunities	<i>wx</i>	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. Tourism in Dumaguete City provides more job opportunities for local residents.	4.23	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Local businesses benefit from the increasing number of tourists.	4.27	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Tourism helps boost the income of small and medium enterprises in the city.	4.23	Strongly Agree	Very High

4. The growth of tourism encourages more investments in Dumaguete City.	4.23	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. Tourism contributes significantly to the overall economic development of the city.	4.27	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.25	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 3.1.2 presents the extent of respondents' perception of the economic opportunities created by tourism in Dumaguete City as perceived by business owners. The results reflect how entrepreneurs evaluated the economic benefits generated by tourism activities in the city. The composite mean of 3.94, interpreted as "High,"

Table 3.2.1 presents the extent of respondents' perception of the social and cultural opportunities created by tourism in Dumaguete City as perceived by tourism staff. The composite mean of 4.44, interpreted as "Very High," shows that tourism is viewed as a strong contributor to social and cultural development in the city. Tourism raises awareness and appreciation of local culture and traditions obtained the highest mean of 4.55.

Table 3.1.2
Extent of the Respondents' Perception of the Opportunities created by Tourism in Dumaguete City in terms of Economic Opportunities as Perceived by Business Owner

Economic Opportunities	\bar{wx}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. Tourism in Dumaguete City provides more job opportunities for local residents.	3.83	Agree	High
2. Local businesses benefit from the increasing number of tourists.	3.97	Agree	High
3. Tourism helps boost the income of small and medium enterprises in the city.	4.03	Agree	High
4. The growth of tourism encourages more investments in Dumaguete City.	3.97	Agree	High
5. Tourism contributes significantly to the overall economic development of the city.	3.91	Agree	High
Composite	3.94	Agree	High

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 3.2.2 presents the extent of respondents' perception of the social and cultural opportunities created by tourism in Dumaguete City as viewed by tourists. The composite mean of 4.41, interpreted as "Very High," reflects that tourists see tourism as a strong support for the city's social and cultural development. Among the indicators, greater understanding and appreciation of local culture and traditions obtained the highest mean of 4.47.

Table 3.2.3 presents the extent of respondents' perception of the social and cultural opportunities created by tourism in Dumaguete City as perceived by business owners. The indicator local residents take pride in sharing their customs and traditions with visitors obtained the highest mean score of 4.29, interpreted as "very high."

Table 3.2.1
Extent of the Respondents' Perception of the Opportunities created by Tourism in Dumaguete City in terms of Social and Cultural Opportunities as Perceived by Tourism Staff

Social and Cultural Opportunities	$\bar{w}x$	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. Tourism promotes awareness and appreciation of Dumaguete City's culture and traditions.	4.55	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. The interaction between tourists and locals strengthens cultural exchange.	4.45	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Tourism helps preserve the city's cultural heritage and historical sites.	4.45	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. Local residents take pride in sharing their customs and traditions with visitors.	4.27	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. Tourism encourages community participation in cultural and local events.	4.45	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.44	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 3.2.2
Extent of the Respondents' Perception of the Opportunities created by Tourism in Dumaguete City in terms of Social and Cultural Opportunities as Perceived by Tourist

Social and Cultural Opportunities	$\bar{w}x$	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. Tourism promotes awareness and appreciation of Dumaguete City's culture and traditions.	4.47	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. The interaction between tourists and locals strengthens cultural exchange.	4.31	Strongly Agree	Very High

3. Tourism helps preserve the city's cultural heritage and historical sites.	4.41	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. Local residents take pride in sharing their customs and traditions with visitors.	4.41	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. Tourism encourages community participation in cultural and local events.	4.43	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.41	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 3.2.3
Extent of the Respondents' Perception of the Opportunities created by Tourism in Dumaguete City in terms of Social and Cultural Opportunities as Perceived by Business Owner

Social and Cultural Opportunities	<i>wx</i>	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. Tourism promotes awareness and appreciation of Dumaguete City's culture and traditions.	4.20	Agree	High
2. The interaction between tourists and locals strengthens cultural exchange.	4.09	Agree	High
3. Tourism helps preserve the city's cultural heritage and historical sites.	4.11	Agree	High
4. Local residents take pride in sharing their customs and traditions with visitors.	4.29	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. Tourism encourages community participation in cultural and local events.	4.26	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.19	Agree	High

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 4.1.1 presents the perceived challenges related to infrastructure and facilities in Dumaguete City as identified by tourism staff. The indicator inadequate road networks make access to tourist destinations difficult obtained the highest mean score of 3.41, interpreted as "High."

Table 4.1.1
Extent of the Respondents' Perception of the Opportunities created by Tourism in Dumaguete City in terms of Infrastructure and Facilities Challenges as Perceived by Tourism Staff

Infrastructure and Facilities Challenges	\bar{w}_x	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. Inadequate road networks make access to tourist destinations difficult.	3.41	Agree	High
2. The lack of sufficient public facilities (e.g., restrooms, signage, parking areas) affects tourists' comfort.	3.14	Moderately Agree	Moderate
3. Poor maintenance of infrastructure limits the city's tourism potential.	3.23	Moderately Agree	Moderate
4. The city lacks enough accommodation facilities to cater to a large number of tourists.	2.68	Moderately Agree	Moderate
5. Transportation services to and from tourist spots are unreliable.	2.77	Moderately Agree	Moderate
Composite	3.05	Moderately Agree	Moderate

Legend: **Scale** **Verbal Description** **Verbal Equivalent**
 4.21 – 5.00 Strongly Agree Very High
 3.41 – 4.20 Agree High
 2.61 – 3.40 Moderately Agree Moderate
 1.81 – 2.60 Disagree Low
 1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree Very Low

Table 4.1.2 presents the perceived infrastructure and facility-related challenges in Dumaguete City based on tourists' responses. The indicator lack of sufficient public facilities affects tourists' comfort obtained the highest mean score of 3.91, interpreted as "High."

Table 4.1.2
Extent of the Respondents' Perception of the Opportunities created by Tourism in Dumaguete City in terms of Infrastructure and Facilities Challenges as Perceived by Tourist

Infrastructure and Facilities Challenges	\bar{w}_x	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. Inadequate road networks make access to tourist destinations difficult.	3.83	Agree	High
2. The lack of sufficient public facilities (e.g., restrooms, signage, parking areas) affects tourists' comfort.	3.91	Agree	High
3. Poor maintenance of infrastructure limits the city's tourism potential.	3.73	Agree	High
4. The city lacks enough accommodation facilities to cater to a large number of tourists.	3.52	Agree	High
5. Transportation services to and from tourist spots are unreliable.	3.42	Agree	High
Composite	3.68	Agree	High

Legend: **Scale** **Verbal Description** **Verbal Equivalent**
 4.21 – 5.00 Strongly Agree Very High
 3.41 – 4.20 Agree High
 2.61 – 3.40 Moderately Agree Moderate
 1.81 – 2.60 Disagree Low

1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree

Very Low

Table 4.1.3 presents the perceived infrastructure and facility-related challenges in Dumaguete City as viewed by business owners. The indicator poor maintenance of infrastructure limits the city’s tourism potential obtained the highest mean score of 3.83, interpreted as “High.”

Table 4.1.3
Extent of the Respondents’ Perception of the Opportunities created by Tourism in Dumaguete City in terms of Infrastructure and Facilities Challenges as Perceived by Business Owner

Infrastructure and Facilities Challenges	\bar{w}_x	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. Inadequate road networks make access to tourist destinations difficult.	3.69	Agree	High
2. The lack of sufficient public facilities (e.g., restrooms, signage, parking areas) affects tourists’ comfort.	3.80	Agree	High
3. Poor maintenance of infrastructure limits the city’s tourism potential.	3.83	Agree	High
4. The city lacks enough accommodation facilities to cater to a large number of tourists.	3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
5. Transportation services to and from tourist spots are unreliable.	3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
Composite	3.62	Agree	High

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 4.2.1 presents the environmental challenges affecting tourism in Dumaguete City as perceived by tourism staff. The indicator overcrowding in popular tourist areas leads to environmental degradation obtained the highest mean score of 3.50, interpreted as “high.” In comparison, some natural attractions are not properly protected or conserved recorded the lowest mean score of 3.27, interpreted as “Moderately high.” The composite mean of 3.36, interpreted as “Moderately high,” suggests that environmental challenges are recognized but are not yet considered severe.

Table 4.2.2 presents the environmental challenges affecting tourism in Dumaguete City as perceived by tourists. The indicator pollution and waste management issues negatively affect the city’s tourist attractions obtained the highest mean score of 3.96, interpreted as “High.” s are considered existing issues that may affect tourism in the city.

Table 4.2.1
Extent of the Respondents' Perception of the Opportunities created by Tourism in Dumaguete City in terms of Environmental Challenges as Perceived by Tourism Staff

Environmental Challenges	$\bar{w}x$	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. Pollution and waste management issues negatively affect the city's tourist attractions.	3.32	Moderately Agree	Moderate
2. Overcrowding in popular tourist areas leads to environmental degradation.	3.50	Agree	High
3. Some natural attractions are not properly protected or conserved.	3.27	Moderately Agree	Moderate
4. The lack of environmental awareness among visitors contributes to tourism-related problems.	3.36	Moderately Agree	Moderate
5. Climate-related issues (e.g., flooding, typhoons) pose challenges to tourism activities.	3.36	Moderately Agree	Moderate
Composite	3.36	Moderately Agree	Moderate

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 4.2.3 presents the environmental challenges affecting tourism in Dumaguete City as perceived by business owners. The indicator climate-related issues pose challenges to tourism activities obtained the highest mean score of 4.09, interpreted as "High." On the other hand, some natural attractions are not properly protected or conserved recorded the lowest mean score of 3.08, still interpreted as "High." The composite mean of 3.95, interpreted as "High," indicates that environmental challenges are viewed as important factors that may influence tourism development.

Table 4.2.2
Extent of the Respondents' Perception of the Opportunities created by Tourism in Dumaguete City in terms of Environmental Challenges as Perceived by Tourist

Environmental Challenges	$\bar{w}x$	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. Pollution and waste management issues negatively affect the city's tourist attractions.	3.96	Agree	High
2. Overcrowding in popular tourist areas leads to environmental degradation.	3.91	Agree	High
3. Some natural attractions are not properly protected or conserved.	3.73	Agree	High
4. The lack of environmental awareness among visitors contributes to tourism-related problems.	3.85	Agree	High

5. Climate-related issues (e.g., flooding, typhoons) pose challenges to tourism activities.	3.75	Agree	High
Composite	3.84	Agree	High
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 4.2.3
Extent of the Respondents’ Perception of the Opportunities created by Tourism in Dumaguete City in terms of Environmental Challenges as Perceived by Business Owner

Environmental Challenges	$\bar{w}x$	Verbal Description	Verbal Description
1. Pollution and waste management issues negatively affect the city’s tourist attractions.	4.03	Agree	High
2. Overcrowding in popular tourist areas leads to environmental degradation.	3.97	Agree	High
3. Some natural attractions are not properly protected or conserved.	3.80	Agree	High
4. The lack of environmental awareness among visitors contributes to tourism-related problems.	3.86	Agree	High
5. Climate-related issues (e.g., flooding, typhoons) pose challenges to tourism activities.	4.09	Agree	High
Composite	3.95	Agree	High
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 5.1.1 presents the relationship between the tourism profile of Dumaguete City and respondents’ level of satisfaction. Among the indicators, tourism services recorded the strongest relationship with satisfaction ($r = 0.793$), followed infrastructure and facilities ($r = 0.607$), and tourist attractions ($r = 0.597$). A very strong relationship is observed between infrastructure and facilities and satisfaction ($r = 0.907$), highlighting the critical role of well-developed infrastructure in enhancing visitor experience. In addition, strong associations are also seen between infrastructure and tourist attractions ($r = 0.803$), and between promotion and tourism services ($r = 0.771$). Although other relationships, such as tourist attractions with promotion and marketing strategies ($r = 0.431$) and tourism services with tourist attractions ($r = 0.459$), show moderate correlations.

Table 5.1.1
Significant Relationship between the Current Tourism Profile and the Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of the Dumaguete Tourism Potentials as Perceived by Tourism Staff

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Tourist Attraction				
Tourist Attraction	0.597	0.003	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Infrastructure and Facilities	0.607	0.003	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Tourism Services	0.793	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Promotion and Marketing Strategies	0.728	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Infrastructure and Facilities				
Tourist Attraction	0.803	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Infrastructure and Facilities	0.907	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Tourism Services	0.644	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Promotion and Marketing Strategies	0.629	0.002	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Tourism Services				
Tourist Attraction	0.459	0.032	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Infrastructure and Facilities	0.651	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Tourism Services	0.663	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Promotion and Marketing Strategies	0.619	0.002	Reject H ₀₁	Significant

Table 5.1.2 presents the relationship between the tourism profile of Dumaguete City and respondents' level of satisfaction. Among the indicators, tourism services show the strongest associations with satisfaction ($r = 0.577$ and $r = 0.671$), suggesting that service quality plays a central role in shaping tourist experiences and infrastructure and facilities ($r = 0.647$) also show moderately strong relationships, indicating that these factors meaningfully influence visitor satisfaction. In comparison, some relationships, such as infrastructure under promotion ($r = 0.287$), are weaker but remain statistically significant.

Table 5.1.2
Significant Relationship between the Current Tourism Profile and the Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of the Dumaguete Tourism Potentials as Perceived by Tourist

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Tourist Attraction				
Tourist Attraction	0.488	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Infrastructure and Facilities	0.330	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant

Tourism Services	0.577	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Promotion and Marketing Strategies	0.537	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Infrastructure and Facilities				
Tourist Attraction	0.535	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Infrastructure and Facilities	0.647	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Tourism Services	0.445	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Promotion and Marketing Strategies	0.392	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Tourism Services				
Tourist Attraction	0.671	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Infrastructure and Facilities	0.549	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Tourism Services	0.527	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Promotion and Marketing Strategies	0.550	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant

Table 5.1.3 presents the relationship between the tourism profile of Dumaguete City and respondents' level of satisfaction. Among the indicators, tourist attractions show strong relationships with infrastructure and facilities ($r = 0.660$), tourism services ($r = 0.626$), and Infrastructure and facilities also exhibit moderate relationships with tourism services ($r = 0.568$) and promotion and marketing strategies ($r = 0.558$), indicating that well-developed infrastructure contributes to better service delivery and more effective promotional outcomes. In addition, its internal correlation ($r = 0.487$), although moderate, remains significant, confirming its consistent influence on satisfaction.

Table 5.1.3
Significant Relationship between the Current Tourism Profile and the Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of the Dumaguete Tourism Potentials as Perceived by Business Owner

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Tourist Attraction				
Infrastructure and Facilities	0.660	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Tourism Services	0.626	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Infrastructure and Facilities				
Infrastructure and Facilities	0.487	0.003	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Tourism Services	0.568	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant

DISCUSSION

The current tourism profile of Dumaguete City

1.1.1 Tourism site perceived by Tourism staff

Table 1.1.1 presents the tourism staff's perception of the tourism sites in Dumaguete City, focusing on various attractions and their contribution to the city's overall tourism appeal. The results show a composite mean of 4.75, interpreted as "very high," which indicates that respondents have had a very positive assessment of the city as a tourism destination. Rizal Boulevard has obtained the highest mean of 4.95, followed by the Bell Tower of St. Catherine of Alexandria Cathedral with a mean of 4.82. In contrast, the lowest mean has been recorded at 4.45, referring to the statement that Dumaguete City offers a wide variety of tourist attractions that cater to different interests. ill interpreted as "very high," showing that all indicators have been rated positively. This supports the idea that tourist satisfaction has depended more on the quality and management of attractions rather than the number of attractions alone (Cano et al., 2021).

1.1.2 Tourism site perceived by Tourist

Table 1.1.2 presents the perception of tourists regarding the tourism sites in Dumaguete City. It has described how visitors have evaluated key attractions in terms of appeal, atmosphere, clarity of information, cultural value, and culinary contribution to the city's tourism image. The composite mean of 4.43, interpreted as "very high," indicates that tourists have had a very positive perception of the city's tourism sites. Rizal Boulevard has obtained the highest rating with a mean of 4.53, reflecting its relaxing and enjoyable atmosphere for both tourists and locals. This has been followed by the Bell Tower of St. Catherine of Alexandria Cathedral with a mean of 4.51, which has been recognized as a culturally and historically important site that has strengthened the city's tourism appeal. In contrast, the National Museum of the Philippines Dumaguete has received the lowest rating of 4.35 in terms of clarity of information, although it has still been interpreted as "very high." Gayeta and Ylagan (2022) have emphasized the importance of cultural heritage attractions in shaping tourists' experiences in the Philippines.

1.1.3 Tourism site perceived by Business owner

Table 1.1.3 presents the assessment of business owners regarding the tourism sites in Dumaguete City. It shows how local entrepreneurs perceive the city's major attractions and their contribution to the overall tourism profile. The composite mean of 4.22, interpreted as "very high," indicates that business owners generally have a favorable perception of the city's tourism sites. Rizal Boulevard and Sans Rival Bistro & Bakery obtained the highest mean of 4.34 and were both interpreted as "strongly agree." This indicates that business owners view the boulevard's relaxing atmosphere and the popularity of local delicacies as significant contributors to the city's tourism appeal. In contrast, the item on the variety of tourist attractions in Dumaguete City received the lowest mean of 4.00, interpreted as "high," although it still reflects a positive assessment. Yi et al. (2025) found that tourists' perceived authenticity of cultural heritage architecture significantly influences aesthetic appreciation and word-of-mouth behavior, highlighting the importance of cultural and architectural authenticity in shaping visitor satisfaction.

1.2.1 Infrastructure and Facilities perceived by Tourism staff

Table 1.2.1 Indicators stating that the city has adequate safety and security measures for tourists assessed by tourism staff got a highest mean score of 4.59, interpreted as Strongly Agree. The tourism staff perceive that Dumaguete City as a safe and secure destination, which essential for attracting and maintaining visitors. The study implies that the city's strong safety and security measures serve as a key strength in supporting tourism development, raising visitor confidence and promoting a positive image that can boost Dumaguete City's tourism potential. The lowest mean score among the indicators under infrastructure and facilities for tourism staff is the Communication networks (internet, mobile signal) are reliable in all tourist areas got a mean score of 4.00, interpreted as high. This indicate that improving communication could support tourism staff in giving efficient services, and maintaining better communication with tourist. According to Sitones and Meñez (2024) investigated hotel attributes, guest experiences, and satisfaction among Department of Tourism (DOT) accredited Mabuhay accommodation establishments in the Caraga Region, Philippines, and found that accommodation attributes such as comfort, amenities, and service quality strongly influenced overall guest satisfaction.

1.2.2 Infrastructure and Facilities perceived by Tourist

Table 1.2.2 The indicator accommodation facilities (hotels, inns, resorts) are comfortable and affordable gain the highest mean score of 4.14, interpreted as Agree. This means that tourist says that the accommodation establishments in Dumaguete City provides a satisfactory level of comfort and affordable prices. The study implies that the availability and affordable accommodations promote positive experience of tourist and encourage to stay longer. The lowest mean of the indicator public facilities is clean and functional got a mean score of 3.81, interpreted as Agree. This emphasizes that while tourist find a public facility, still there are areas that needs improvement especially in cleanliness and functionality. In other words, developing public facilities and maintenance could improve tourist satisfaction. Sitones and Meñez (2024) emphasized that the quality and comfort of accommodation facilities play a central role in shaping tourists' overall satisfaction and destination image.

1.2.3 Infrastructure and Facilities perceived by Business owner

Table 1.2.3 The data present that the highest mean score of 4.17 is the indicator accommodation facilities are comfortable and affordable, which interpreted as Agree. The business owners indicates that the accommodation establishments in Dumaguete City provides affordability and comfort for tourist. So, the implication in this study attracts more visitors and encouraged them to stay longer through quality and reasonably priced accommodations. Furthermore, the indicator public facilities are clean and functional had a lowest mean score of 3.20, interpreted as Moderately high by the business owner. Business owners seen those public facilities as moderately satisfactory in terms of functionality and cleanliness. In addition, if the quality, cleanliness and maintenance of public facilities will improve, this will help the overall tourist experience to support local tourism businesses. Therefore, the composite mean score of 3.71, interpreted as high, shows the infrastructure and facilities in Dumaguete City as adequate in supporting tourism and related business activities. This implies that transportation, accommodations,

and communication services are functional for tourism operations. They found that accommodation features perceived as comfortable, innovative, and well managed significantly increase guests' positive experiences and their willingness to revisit or recommend the destination. Comfortable and affordable accommodation facilities enhance both visitor satisfaction and business outcomes in tourism destinations (Dai et al., 2025).

1.3.1 Tourism Services perceived by Tourism staff

Table 1.3.1 Perceived by the tourism staff with the indicator of tour guides are knowledgeable and accommodating obtained the highest mean of 4.77, interpreted as Strongly Agree. This means that Dumaguete City is highly competent in giving information's and providing quality service to tourist. This demonstrates that tour guides have a huge part in enhancing tourist experiences by giving right knowledge about destinations. The result implies that the preparedness of tour guides contributes positively to the services of tourism. The two indicators some restaurants in Dumaguete City provide quality local and international food and tour packages and activities meet tourist's expectations both got the lowest mean of 4.55, interpreted as very high. This indicates that tourism staff perceive tourism services positively, but these indicators received a lowest rating compared with other indicators this means there are areas that need improvement. Knowledgeable tour guides, well-organized tour packages, and the quality of food services contribute to have a positive tourism experience. The importance of safe and efficient transportation services in creating positive experiences for travelers, supporting the notion that transportation services perceived as safe, efficient, and tourist friendly contribute positively to visitor's overall impressions of a destination (Velastegui-Hernández, R., et al. (2024)

1.3.2 Tourism Services perceived by Tourist

Table 1.3.2 The indicator stating tourism office provides excellent customer service obtained the highest mean of 4.17, interpreted as Agree, indicating that tourists have a positive insight of the customer service given by the tourism office in Dumaguete City. This proved that tourism office is able to accommodate visitors effectively by giving information, and guidance during their stay. The result expresses the importance task of the tourism office in ensuring that visitors feel welcomed. In this table the indicator got the lowest mean score of 4.08, interpreted as Agree is the transportation services are safe, efficient, and tourist friendly perceived by the tourist. This shows that even if transportation is safe and functional, still there are areas that need improvement in terms of accessibility, efficiency. As an implication, transport providers and local tourism authorities should develop or expand transportation services. Therefore, the composite mean of 4.18, which is interpreted as high, viewed that tourists have a positive insight of the tourism services in Dumaguete City. Various aspects of the tour experience, including itinerary, guiding services, and activity quality, affect tourist's levels of satisfaction and their overall evaluation of a trip, Hwang et al., (2023). Their findings indicated that higher perceived tour quality comprising well-organized activities, appropriate pacing, and fulfilling experiences was positively associated with greater tourist satisfaction.

The Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Tourism Potentials of Dumaguete City

2.1.1 Tourism site perceived by Tourism staff

Table 2.1.1 shows that the indicator experience and enjoyment in visiting tourist attractions obtained the highest mean score of 4.59, interpreted as “Very Satisfied.” This indicates that tourism staff observed that tourists generally had positive and enjoyable experiences when visiting Dumaguete City. The results suggest that the city’s tourism destinations provide memorable experiences and a pleasant environment for visitors. This implies that the overall appeal of Dumaguete City’s attractions is important in maintaining its image as an attractive tourism destination. In contrast, the indicator availability of informative signages and guides at tourist sites obtained the lowest mean score of 4.41. This means that tourists were satisfied with the existing signages and guides, as these helped them navigate and understand the sites they visited. However, there are areas for improvement, particularly in terms of clarity, visibility, and the number of informational materials available. The experience and enjoyment of tourists play a key role in shaping their overall satisfaction and perception of a destination. Positive travel experiences can increase the likelihood of repeat visits and encourage favorable word-of-mouth, which supports the long-term sustainability of tourism destinations (Huang et al., 2023).

2.1.2 Tourism site perceived by Tourist

Table 2.1.2 shows that the indicator experience and enjoyment in visiting tourist attractions obtained the highest mean score of 4.39, interpreted as “Very Satisfied.” This indicates that the tourism sites in Dumaguete City provide engaging activities and memorable experiences that contribute to tourist satisfaction. The result implies that the tourism sector should continue maintaining and expanding the appeal of its attractions to encourage repeat visits and strengthen the city’s image as a tourist destination. In contrast, the lowest mean score of 4.03 was recorded for the cleanliness and maintenance of attractions in Rizal Boulevard. This was interpreted as “Satisfied,” which shows that tourists generally find the area acceptable, although improvements are still needed. While visitors may not have fully met their expectations in terms of cleanliness and maintenance, they still recognize Rizal Boulevard as a key attraction in the city. This finding implies that local government units and the tourism office should prioritize cleanliness and proper maintenance to enhance the city’s overall image. Tourist experience and satisfaction play an important role in assessing the tourism potential of a destination because they influence how visitors perceive and enjoy attractions. In Dumaguete City, studies on heritage tourism have shown that visitors have better experiences when attractions provide well-organized exhibits, quality services, and accessible facilities, which enhance overall enjoyment (Ausejo et al., 2025).

2.2.1 Infrastructure and Facilities perceived by Tourism staff

Table 2.2.1 shows that the availability of accommodation that meets tourists’ needs obtained the highest mean score of 4.32, interpreted as “Very Satisfied.” This indicates that lodging options in Dumaguete City are generally accessible and suitable for different types of visitors. The result suggests that further enhancing the quality and diversity of lodging facilities may contribute to higher levels of visitor satisfaction. In contrast, the

accessibility of roads and transportation to tourist sites received the lowest mean score of 4.18, interpreted as “Satisfied.” This implies that while transport services and road networks are generally functional, some visitors still experience difficulty reaching certain attractions efficiently. Laspiñas and Tayco (2025) emphasized that well-managed and accessible accommodation facilities contribute significantly to tourist comfort and satisfaction, as many establishments strive to improve service quality and sustainability.

2.2.2 Infrastructure and Facilities perceived by Tourist

Table 2.2.2 shows that the availability of accommodation that meets tourists’ needs obtained the highest mean score of 4.11, interpreted as “Satisfied.” This indicates that lodging facilities in Dumaguete City are generally able to meet the basic needs of visitors during their stay. It also suggests that most establishments provide an acceptable level of comfort for tourists. This finding implies that stakeholders should continue improving the quality and affordability of lodging services to further enhance visitor satisfaction. On the other hand, the availability of public facilities received the lowest mean score of 3.95, also interpreted as “Satisfied.” This suggests that while public facilities are present and functional, some tourists have not fully experienced satisfaction in terms of cleanliness, availability, or accessibility. It highlights the need for stronger collaboration between the local government and tourism partners to improve maintenance and enhance convenience for visitors. Lopez (2025) emphasized that access to suitable accommodation plays a major role in shaping tourists’ overall experience, as varied lodging options that match different budgets and preferences help increase comfort and satisfaction.

2.2.3 Infrastructure and Facilities perceived by Business owner

Table 2.2.3 shows that the availability of accommodation that meets tourists’ needs obtained the highest mean score of 4.03, interpreted as “Satisfied.” This indicates that business owners perceive Dumaguete City as having lodging establishments that adequately cater to visitors. It also suggests that these facilities are accessible and capable of supporting tourist arrivals. This finding implies that maintaining and continuously improving accommodation services can help sustain visitor satisfaction and support the city’s tourism development. Meanwhile, the availability of public facilities recorded the lowest mean score of 3.37, interpreted as “Moderately Satisfied.” This suggests that although such facilities are present, business owners believe that improvements are still needed to fully meet tourists’ needs. Lopez (2025) emphasized that offering a variety of accommodation options improves tourists’ experiences while also attracting more customers to local enterprises.

2.3.1 Tourism Services perceived by Tourism staff

Table 2.3.1 shows that the indicator hospitality and friendliness of locals obtained the highest mean score of 4.82, interpreted as “Very Satisfied.” This indicates that tourism staff perceive Dumaguete City as highly welcoming, accommodating, and friendly to tourists. Such positive interactions contribute greatly to visitors’ overall experience. Sustaining this strength may further enhance the city’s image as a hospitable destination and encourage positive word-of-mouth promotion. On the other hand, the indicator availability and quality of local tour guides received the lowest mean score of 4.50,

although it is still interpreted as “Very Satisfied.” This suggests that tour guides are generally capable of delivering quality service, but there is still room for improvement compared to other service aspects. Unurlu (2024) emphasized that the friendliness and hospitality of local residents strongly influence tourists’ experiences, as welcoming interactions make visitors feel more comfortable and satisfied.

2.3.2 Tourism Services perceived by Tourist

Table 2.3.2 shows that the indicator food services and restaurants in Dumaguete obtained the highest mean score of 4.41, interpreted as “Very Satisfied.” This indicates that tourists are pleased with the quality and accessibility of food options in Dumaguete City. The result highlights the city’s strong potential in offering culinary experiences that appeal to both local and international tastes. In comparison, the indicators availability and quality of local tour guides and responsiveness of tourism offices to inquiries both received the lowest mean score of 4.21, although still interpreted as “Very Satisfied.” This suggests that tourists consider these services reliable and helpful, but they received slightly lower ratings than other aspects. Enhancing training programs for tour guides and improving the responsiveness of tourism offices may further strengthen service quality and ensure that visitors receive accurate and timely information. Martín et al. (2021) emphasized that food services and restaurants play a vital role in shaping tourists’ experiences, as the quality of food, service, and dining environment significantly influence satisfaction and how visitors remember and recommend a destination.

2.3.3 Tourism Services perceived by Business owner

Table 2.3.3 shows that the indicator food services and restaurants in Dumaguete obtained the highest mean score of 4.54, interpreted as “Very Satisfied.” This indicates that business owners perceive the city’s food establishments as making a strong contribution to tourism development and visitor experiences in Dumaguete City. The result highlights the importance of the local food sector in enhancing the destination’s appeal. The indicator responsiveness of tourism offices to inquiries recorded the lowest mean score of 3.80, interpreted as “Satisfied.” This shows that although the service is acceptable, there are still areas that need improvement. Trivenna and Eviana (2024) explained that higher tourist satisfaction benefits local businesses by encouraging longer stays, increased spending, and positive word-of-mouth.

The extent of the respondents’ perception of the opportunities created by tourism in Dumaguete City

3.1.1 Economic Opportunities perceived by Tourism staff

Table 3.1.1 presents the extent of respondents’ perception of the economic opportunities generated by tourism in Dumaguete City as perceived by tourism staff. The findings show a composite mean of 4.25, interpreted as “Strongly Agree” and “Very High,” indicating that tourism staff perceive tourism as generating substantial economic opportunities for the city. Local businesses benefiting from the increasing number of tourists and tourism contributing significantly to overall economic development both obtained a mean of 4.27. These results suggest that respondents strongly recognize tourism’s role in driving business growth and supporting the city’s economic progress.

Slightly lower yet still very high ratings, each with a mean of 4.23, were observed for indicators related to job creation for local residents, increased income for small and medium enterprises, and the encouragement of investment in the city. These findings indicate that while all economic aspects are positively perceived, their impacts are viewed with relatively similar strength. The results imply that tourism serves as a major contributor to Dumaguete City's economic development by supporting businesses, generating employment, increasing enterprise income, and attracting investments. Alcalá Olid et al. (2025) noted that the tourism sector contributes to the economy of major destinations by generating both direct and indirect employment opportunities while also stimulating local production through multiplier effects.

3.1.2 Economic Opportunities perceived by Business owner

Table 3.1.2 presents the extent of respondents' perception of the economic opportunities created by tourism in Dumaguete City as perceived by business owners. The results reflect how entrepreneurs evaluated the economic benefits generated by tourism activities in the city. The composite mean of 3.94, interpreted as "High," indicates that business owners view tourism as generating considerable economic opportunities. Indicators such as tourism helps boost the income of small and medium enterprises (mean = 4.03), as well as local businesses benefit from the increasing number of tourists and the growth of tourism encourages more investments in Dumaguete City (both with a mean of 3.97), received the highest ratings. These results suggest that business owners strongly recognize tourism's role in increasing enterprise income, stimulating business activity, and attracting investments. In comparison, tourism provides more job opportunities for local residents obtained the lowest mean of 3.83. While still rated positively, this suggests that employment generation is perceived as slightly less strong compared to other economic benefits. The OECD (2022) reported that tourism recovery and growth enhance business cash flow and create opportunities for expansion and innovation.

3.2.1 Social and Cultural Opportunities perceived by Tourism staff

Table 3.2.1 presents the extent of respondents' perception of the social and cultural opportunities created by tourism in Dumaguete City as perceived by tourism staff. The findings describe how tourism contributes to cultural awareness, heritage protection, community involvement, and cultural interaction. The composite mean of 4.44, interpreted as "Very High," shows that tourism is viewed as a strong contributor to social and cultural development in the city. Tourism raises awareness and appreciation of local culture and traditions obtained the highest mean of 4.55. Three indicators shared the same mean of 4.45: interaction between tourists and locals strengthens cultural exchange, tourism supports the preservation of cultural heritage and historical sites, and tourism encourages participation in cultural and community events. The lowest rating, with a mean of 4.27, was local residents take pride in sharing their customs and traditions with visitors. The results suggest that tourism helps strengthen cultural understanding, support heritage preservation, encourage community participation, and promote meaningful interaction between residents and visitors. Lan et al. (2021) noted that cultural heritage tourism not only brings economic benefits but also enhances residents' pride and strengthens their sense of cultural identity.

3.2.2 Social and Cultural Opportunities perceived by Tourist

Table 3.2.2 presents the extent of respondents' perception of the social and cultural opportunities created by tourism in Dumaguete City as viewed by tourists. It describes how visitors assessed tourism's influence on cultural understanding, heritage protection, and community involvement. The composite mean of 4.41, interpreted as "Very High," reflects that tourists see tourism as a strong support for the city's social and cultural development. Among the indicators, greater understanding and appreciation of local culture and traditions obtained the highest mean of 4.47. Close to this, active participation in cultural and community activities recorded a mean of 4.43. At the lower end, though still highly rated, interaction between visitors and residents that promotes cultural sharing registered a mean of 4.31. The results indicate that tourism is widely perceived by visitors as a means of deepening cultural appreciation and encouraging participation in local traditions and events, while also supporting cultural continuity within the community. Geçikli et al. (2024) pointed out that cultural tourism plays an important role in safeguarding heritage by encouraging the proper management and continuation of historical assets.

3.2.3 Social and Cultural Opportunities perceived by Business owner

Table 3.2.3 presents the extent of respondents' perception of the social and cultural opportunities created by tourism in Dumaguete City as perceived by business owners. It reflects how they view tourism's influence on cultural identity, community involvement, and interaction between residents and visitors. The indicator local residents take pride in sharing their customs and traditions with visitors obtained the highest mean score of 4.29, interpreted as "very high." This shows that business owners recognize tourism as a factor that strengthens cultural identity and reinforces community pride. On the other hand, interaction between tourists and locals strengthens cultural exchange recorded the lowest mean score of 4.09, interpreted as "high." This suggests that while cultural interaction is present, there is still room to improve engagement between visitors and residents. Zhang et al. (2023) emphasized that heritage tourism plays an important role in transmitting culture, allowing tourists to better understand historical and cultural values. They further explained that tourism experiences involving cultural sites, traditions, and local communities help visitors develop greater appreciation and respect for cultural diversity.

The extent of the respondents' perception of the challenges affecting tourism development in Dumaguete City

4.1.1 Infrastructure and Facilities Challenges perceived by Tourism staff

Table 4.1.1 presents the perceived challenges related to infrastructure and facilities in Dumaguete City as identified by tourism staff. The results highlight key issues that affect accessibility and the overall convenience of visiting tourist destinations. The indicator inadequate road networks make access to tourist destinations difficult obtained the highest mean score of 3.41, interpreted as "High." This suggests that tourism staff consider road accessibility a major concern, as it directly affects how easily visitors can reach different attractions within the city. In contrast, the indicator the city lacks enough accommodation facilities to cater to a large number of tourists recorded the lowest mean

score of 2.68, interpreted as “Moderately High.” This indicates that although accommodation capacity is seen as a concern, it is viewed as less critical compared to transportation-related issues. The composite mean of 3.05, interpreted as “Moderately High,” shows that respondents generally perceive infrastructure and facility-related concerns as moderate challenges to the city’s tourism development. These findings suggest that improving transportation systems and maintaining essential facilities should be prioritized to enhance visitor convenience and support tourism growth. Cheng et al. (2022) emphasized that transportation infrastructure, particularly road networks, plays a crucial role in tourism development by improving connectivity and accessibility.

4.1.2 Infrastructure and Facilities Challenges perceived by Tourist

Table 4.1.2 presents the perceived infrastructure and facility-related challenges in Dumaguete City based on tourists’ responses. The results highlight factors that influence visitor comfort and accessibility while exploring the city. The indicator lack of sufficient public facilities affects tourists’ comfort obtained the highest mean score of 3.91, interpreted as “High.” This indicates that visitors consider the availability of public amenities such as restrooms, seating areas, and basic services as essential to a comfortable travel experience. On the other hand, transportation services to and from tourist spots are unreliable recorded the lowest mean score of 3.42, also interpreted as “High.” This suggests that although transportation is generally available, some tourists still experience difficulty in accessing attractions due to inconsistency in transport services. The composite mean of 3.68 indicates that infrastructure and facility-related concerns are viewed as notable challenges affecting tourism experiences in the city. These findings suggest that local authorities and tourism stakeholders should focus on improving public facilities, maintaining infrastructure, and strengthening transportation services to enhance visitor satisfaction. Haryanto and Bambang (2022) explained that poorly developed road systems can make travel more difficult, increase travel time, and reduce overall tourist comfort.

4.1.3 Infrastructure and Facilities Challenges perceived by Business owner

Table 4.1.3 presents the perceived infrastructure and facility-related challenges in Dumaguete City as viewed by business owners. The results highlight issues that may affect the city’s ability to sustain and improve its tourism sector. The indicator poor maintenance of infrastructure limits the city’s tourism potential obtained the highest mean score of 3.83, interpreted as “High.” This suggests that business owners see inadequate maintenance as a major concern, as it can reduce the attractiveness and overall quality of the destination. Meanwhile, the indicators the city lacks enough accommodation facilities to cater to a large number of tourists and transportation services to and from tourist spots are unreliable both recorded the lowest mean score of 3.40, interpreted as “Moderately High.” This indicates that although these issues are recognized, they are considered less critical compared to maintenance-related concerns. The composite mean of 3.62, interpreted as “High,” indicates that infrastructure and facility issues are generally viewed as significant challenges affecting tourism opportunities in Dumaguete City. These findings suggest that improving maintenance, upgrading facilities, and ensuring reliable services are essential to support tourism development. Zhang et al. (2022) noted that adequate accommodation capacity is essential for tourism development because it

determines a destination's ability to host visitors and directly affects comfort, accessibility, and service quality.

4.2.1 Environmental Challenges perceived by Tourism staff

Table 4.2.1 presents the environmental challenges affecting tourism in Dumaguete City as perceived by tourism staff. The results highlight key concerns related to sustainability and the condition of natural attractions. The indicator overcrowding in popular tourist areas leads to environmental degradation obtained the highest mean score of 3.50, interpreted as "high." This indicates that tourism staff view overcrowding as a major issue, as it can negatively affect the condition of tourist sites, damage natural resources, and reduce the quality of visitor experiences. In comparison, some natural attractions are not properly protected or conserved recorded the lowest mean score of 3.27, interpreted as "Moderately high." Although it received the lowest rating, the result still shows that concerns about protection and conservation exist, but they are seen as less critical than other environmental issues. The composite mean of 3.36, interpreted as "Moderately high," suggests that environmental challenges are recognized but are not yet considered severe. Cheng and Wu (2021) emphasized that environmental awareness plays an important role in shaping tourists' responsible behavior, particularly in reducing issues such as littering and improper waste disposal.

4.2.2 Environmental Challenges perceived by Tourist

Table 4.2.2 presents the environmental challenges affecting tourism in Dumaguete City as perceived by tourists. The results highlight concerns related to cleanliness, waste management, and environmental protection. The indicator pollution and waste management issues negatively affect the city's tourist attractions obtained the highest mean score of 3.96, interpreted as "High." This indicates that visitors are concerned about cleanliness and proper waste disposal, suggesting that environmental conditions influence their overall travel experience. Meanwhile, the indicator some natural attractions are not properly protected or conserved recorded the lowest mean score of 3.73, also interpreted as "High." This shows that tourists still recognize the importance of protecting natural sites, even if it is viewed as a slightly less pressing issue compared to waste management concerns. The composite mean of 3.84, interpreted as "High," indicates that environmental challenges are considered existing issues that may affect tourism in the city. These findings suggest that strengthening waste management systems, improving cleanliness, and enhancing conservation efforts are essential to maintain the attractiveness of tourist destinations and improve visitor satisfaction. Figueroa and Rotarou (2021) explained that increasing tourism pressure without proper environmental management can result in habitat disturbance, pollution, and the deterioration of natural landscapes.

4.2.3 Environmental Challenges perceived by Business owner

Table 4.2.3 presents the environmental challenges affecting tourism in Dumaguete City as perceived by business owners. The findings emphasize concerns related to climate conditions and environmental management. The indicator climate-related issues pose challenges to tourism activities obtained the highest mean score of 4.09, interpreted as "High." This suggests that business owners recognize how weather conditions and

natural disturbances can directly affect tourism operations, business performance, and visitor arrivals in the city. On the other hand, some natural attractions are not properly protected or conserved recorded the lowest mean score of 3.08, still interpreted as “High.” Although it received the lowest rating, the result indicates that business owners remain aware of the need to protect and conserve natural sites, as these are essential for long-term tourism sustainability. The composite mean of 3.95, interpreted as “High,” indicates that environmental challenges are viewed as important factors that may influence tourism development. These findings highlight the need to address climate-related risks, strengthen environmental protection programs, and promote responsible tourism practices to support the sustainability of tourism businesses in Dumaguete City. Becken and Loehr (2021) explained that climate change affects not only the physical environment of destinations but also tourists’ perceptions, safety concerns, and overall attractiveness.

The relationship between the current tourism profile and the respondents’ level of satisfaction of the Dumaguete tourism potentials.

5.1.1 relationship between the current tourism profile and the respondents’ level of satisfaction of the Dumaguete tourism potentials perceived by Tourism staff

Table 5.1.1 presents the relationship between the tourism profile of Dumaguete City and respondents’ level of satisfaction. The results show that all computed p-values are below the 0.05 level of significance; hence, the null hypothesis is rejected for all variables. This indicates a significant relationship between tourism profile components and tourist satisfaction, particularly in tourist attractions, infrastructure and facilities, tourism services, and promotion and marketing strategies. Among the indicators, tourism services recorded the strongest relationship with satisfaction ($r = 0.793$), followed by infrastructure and facilities ($r = 0.607$), and tourist attractions ($r = 0.597$). This suggests that the quality of tourism services plays the most influential role in shaping how satisfied tourists feel with their overall experience. A very strong relationship is observed between infrastructure and facilities and satisfaction ($r = 0.907$), highlighting the critical role of well-developed infrastructure in enhancing visitor experience. In addition, strong associations are also seen between infrastructure and tourist attractions ($r = 0.803$), and tourism services ($r = 0.771$). These results indicate that the different components of the tourism profile are closely interconnected and collectively contribute to a more positive tourism experience. The findings suggest that tourism services should be prioritized due to their strong influence on satisfaction. Nopriana et al. (2024) highlighted that attractive destinations combined with well-maintained facilities significantly improve tourists’ overall experience. Riyadi et al. (2024) further noted that infrastructure quality directly influences tourist satisfaction by improving accessibility, reducing travel difficulties, and enhancing comfort. Christianingrum et al. (2024) highlighted that experiential and well-designed marketing strategies significantly improve tourist satisfaction and strengthen revisit intentions.

5.1.2 relationship between the current tourism profile and the respondents' level of satisfaction of the Dumaguete tourism potentials perceived by Tourist

Table 5.1.2 presents the relationship between the tourism profile of Dumaguete City and respondents' level of satisfaction. All variables yielded p-values below 0.05, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates a significant relationship between tourism profile components and tourist satisfaction in the city. Among the indicators, tourism services show the strongest associations with satisfaction ($r = 0.577$ and $r = 0.671$), suggesting that service quality plays a central role in shaping tourist experiences. Infrastructure and facilities ($r = 0.647$) also show moderately strong relationships, indicating that these factors meaningfully influence visitor satisfaction. Masimba (2024) emphasized that tourism service quality significantly affects tourists' intention to revisit a destination, as efficient and reliable services lead to positive perceptions and stronger destination loyalty. Lopez (2025) emphasized that accommodation distribution is strongly influenced by infrastructure and accessibility, which directly affects regional tourism development. Travár et al. (2022) also found that high-quality services such as accommodation, transportation, and visitor support improve satisfaction and encourage repeat visits

5.1.3 relationship between the current tourism profile and the respondents' level of satisfaction of the Dumaguete tourism potentials perceived by Business owner

Table 5.1.3 presents the relationship between the tourism profile of Dumaguete City and respondents' level of satisfaction. All variables produced p-values below 0.05, resulting in the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates a significant relationship between tourism profile components and tourist satisfaction in the city. Among the indicators, tourist attractions show strong relationships with infrastructure and facilities ($r = 0.660$), tourism services ($r = 0.626$). This suggests that the effectiveness of tourist attractions is closely linked to the quality of facilities, services, and promotional efforts that support them. Infrastructure and facilities also exhibit moderate relationships with tourism services ($r = 0.568$) and promotion and marketing strategies ($r = 0.558$), indicating that well-developed infrastructure contributes to better service delivery and more effective promotional outcomes. In addition, its internal correlation ($r = 0.487$), although moderate, remains significant, confirming its consistent influence on satisfaction. The results suggest that tourism development in Dumaguete City should be approached in an integrated manner. Strengthening infrastructure is essential, as it supports both tourism services and the quality of attractions. Hussain et al. (2023) explained that high-quality tourism services, including accommodation, hospitality, guided tours, and visitor support, strongly influence tourist satisfaction and loyalty, encouraging repeat visits and positive word-of-mouth.

Conclusions

The study shows that Dumaguete City has strong tourism potential, as tourism staff, tourists, and business owners generally view its tourism site, infrastructure, services, and promotion strategies positively. These factors collectively contribute to visitor satisfaction and the city's appeal as a destination.

Tourism services emerged as the most influential factor in shaping satisfaction, followed by promotion and marketing, infrastructure and facilities, and tourist attractions. The results also confirm that these elements are interconnected improvements in infrastructure enhance service delivery and access to attractions, while effective promotion increases tourist awareness and interest.

However, challenges remain in areas such as infrastructure limitations, transportation, public facilities, environmental management, and coordination among tourism stakeholders. These issues suggest the need for continued improvements in planning, resource allocation, and governance.

Overall, Dumaguete City's tourism sector is performing well but requires sustained development efforts. Strengthening infrastructure, enhancing service quality, improving environmental practices, and reinforcing promotional strategies are essential to maximize its tourism potential and ensure long-term sustainable growth.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the researchers recommend the following to the Local Government Units (LGU), business owners, locals, and travelers:

Local Government Units (LGU) and Tourism Office of Dumaguete City and Province of Negros Oriental

1. Enhance public facilities in key tourist areas.
2. Strengthen waste management and environmental protection.
3. Protect and conserve natural attractions.

Business Owners

4. Improve service quality through staff training and hospitality.
5. Expand and upgrade accommodation facilities.

Locals

6. Maintain hospitable and welcoming attitudes towards visitors.
7. Improve proper waste disposal.

Travelers/ Tourists

8. Provide feedback to help improve services.
9. Practice responsible and respectful travel by observing proper waste disposal, following local rules and guidelines in tourist sites.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study aimed to determine whether Dumaguete City has strong potential to become a leading tourist destination and to identify challenges that need to be addressed by tourism staff, domestic and foreign tourists, and business owners or managers in Negros Oriental. In conducting this research, the researchers strictly followed ethical standards to ensure the rights, dignity, and protection of all respondents. Before the data collection began, it was clearly explained that participation was voluntary. Respondents

were informed that they were not required to participate and that they could refuse or withdraw at any time without any negative consequences.

During the data collection process, the researchers maintained honesty, respect, and neutrality toward all respondents. Participants were given sufficient time and freedom to answer the questionnaire at their own pace. The researchers also ensured that no pressure, influence, or bias affected their responses. After data gathering, respondents were informed that the study was conducted solely for academic purposes and that all collected data would be used exclusively for this purpose.

In addition, artificial intelligence tools were used to assist in language refinement, grammar checking, and clarity improvement of the research writing. However, all interpretations, analysis, and final decisions remained fully under the responsibility of the researchers. Finally, after the completion of data collection and analysis, all survey questionnaires were properly collected, secured, and disposed of responsibly through shredding and safe disposal to ensure confidentiality and protect the privacy of all respondents.

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